

Assessment of prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city in view to develop an information booklet on prevention and management of behavioural problems.

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ABSTRACT

Children's behavior reflects their emotional and developmental growth. For children of sex workers, exposure to stigma, instability, and financial hardship can impact their social and emotional development. This may lead to behavioral issues like anxiety, aggression, hyperactivity, or social difficulties. Early support and intervention are key to nurturing their well-being. The goal of the study was to assess the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city in view to develop an information booklet on prevention and management of behavioural problems.

Objective : To assess the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city in view to develop an information booklet on prevention and management of behavioural problems.

Method: This research employed a quantitative non-experimental descriptive exploratory method. The research was carried out among 113 children in selected areas of the city by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. The information was gathered using a demographic characteristics and self-structured rating scale to assess the behavioural problems. Fisher's exact test was used for the association between selected demographic variables of children of sex workers and behavioural problems.

Result: Result of the study indicating the prevalence of behavioural problems was:

5.3% of the children of sex workers had habit of thumb sucking. 8% of them had habit of nail biting. 8.8% of them had habit of enuresis. 13.3% of them had violent anger. 7.1% of them had nightmares. None of them had encopresis. 4.4% of them had tics. 5.3% of them were stammering.

(Key words – Prevalence, Thumb sucking, Nail biting, Tics, Enuresis, Encopresis, Stammering, Nightmares, and Temper tantrum).

Introduction

Children's behaviours change as they grow, from simple emotions like crying and tantrums to more complicated activities like problem solving and social interactions. However, if these behaviours are not adequately handled, or if a kid is exposed to negative circumstances such as inconsistent discipline, stress, or trauma, typical behaviour can become problematic. Common elements influencing a child's behaviour include heredity, environment, learning, conditioning, and positive reinforcement.

Every young child experiences occasional misbehaviour, defiance, and impulsivity all of which are entirely normal. All the same, some kids exhibit really tough and problematic behaviours that are abnormal for their age. Children's behavioural problems include a wide range of challenges that can affect how they interact with others, control their emotions, and adjust to various social and academic settings. These issues can show as anger, anxiety, depression, social disengagement, or challenges with concentration and controlling one's emotions. While many factors can contribute to behavioural issues, family relationships, socioeconomic status, and environmental influences all play an important effect.

One of the oldest occupations in the world is thought to be sex work. Some people think of it as a regular profession, while many see it as an act of abuse. Children of sex workers usually grow up in situations characterized by social stigma, financial challenges, and insecure living conditions. These aspects can influence their emotional, social, and behavioural development. Children's behavioural issues may include aggression, anxiety, hyperactivity, or difficulties with social interactions.

Children from marginalized or high-risk backgrounds, such as those raised by sex workers, are more likely to develop behavioural problems. Stigma, poverty, exposure to violence, and a lack of stability can all have an impact on their mental well-being, making it more difficult for them to control their behaviour. These issues can have an impact on their academic achievement, interactions with peers and adults, and general development.

Behavioral problems in children are a significant concern globally, with various studies indicating varying prevalence rates. According to the World Health Organization (WHO), approximately 13% of children aged 3 to 17 have a current, diagnosed mental or behavioral health condition.

Need Of The Study

Behavioural problems in children are imperative for early intervention and support, improving their quality of life, enhancing academic success, fostering healthy social development, addressing underlying mental health issues, providing crucial parental support, reducing stigma surrounding mental health, and ultimately, for the betterment of public health. The well-being of children is shaped by the social, emotional, and environmental conditions in which they grow up. Children of sex workers are often raised in environments marked by instability, poverty, exploitation, and social isolation. The combination of these

factors places them at high risk for developing behavioral problems such as aggression, anxiety, depression, attention deficits, and poor peer relationships.

Primary Objective: -

To assess the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city in view to develop an information booklet on prevention and management of behavioural problems.

Secondary Objectives: -

1. To find out the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city.
2. To find association between selected demographic variables and study finding.

Assumption:-

1. There may be cases of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city.
2. The information booklet will be effective in improving the knowledge of mothers about the prevention and management of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city.

Methodology

The current research was designed to assess the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city in view to develop an information booklet on prevention and management of behavioural problems. This research employed a quantitative non-experimental descriptive exploratory method. The research was carried out among 113 children in selected areas of the city by using a non-probability convenient sampling technique. The information was gathered using a demographic characteristics and self-structured rating scale to assess the behavioural problems. Fisher's exact test was used for the association between selected demographic variables of children of sex workers and behavioural problems. Data collection is the process of recruiting participants and gathering information for a research. Administrative approval was acquired in writing. To ensure a truthful answer, the chosen participants were informed about the objective and use of the research and ensured of the anonymity of their replies. Each participant in the research provided written informed permission.

Results

SECTION I - Description of samples based on their demographic characteristics.

Age

In that selected areas 43.4% of the children of sex workers had age 3-6 years, 36.3% of them had age 6-9 years and 20.4% of them had age 9-12 years.

Gender

In that selected areas 51.3% of them were males and 48.7% of them were females.

Education status of children

In that selected areas 46% of them were currently enrolled in school and 54% of them were not enrolled in school.

Care Taker

In that selected areas 64.6% of them had mothers as caretaker, 30.1% of them had foster parents as caretakers and 5.3% of them had other relatives to take care of them.

Exposure To Violence

In that selected areas 10.6% of them were exposed to violence and 89.4% of them were not exposed to violence.

SECTION II

Analysis of data related to the prevalence of behavioural problems among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city.

Behavioural problem	Freq	%
Yes	56	49.6%
No	57	50.4%

49.6% of the children of sex workers had behavioural problems.

Item analysis - Thumb sucking

In the selected areas 5.3% of the children of sex workers were sometimes sucking their thumb. 0.9% of them mentioned that sometimes thumb-sucking result in noticeable harm to the skin of child's thumb or fingers. 0.9% of them mentioned that the child been observed sucking their thumb during daytime activities.

Item analysis- Nail biting

In that selected areas 7.1% of them mentioned that sometimes their children bite nails. 2.7% of them mentioned that sometimes the child engaged in nail biting. 2.7% of them mentioned that they notice their child biting their nails in a day/week sometimes. 0.9% of them mentioned that sometimes the child bites their nails unconsciously, without realizing they are doing it.

Item analysis- Enuresis

In that selected areas 7.1% of them mentioned sometimes and 1.8% of them mentioned frequently child experience episodes of bedwetting. 4.4% of them mentioned that sometimes child typically wake up with a wet bed or wet clothes despite having access to the toilet during the night. 4.4% of them mentioned sometimes had bedwetting caused any disruption to the child's sleep patterns or quality of sleep. 2.7% of them mentioned sometimes child has any daytime urinary symptoms such as urgency or frequency.

Item analysis- Act violent anger

In that selected areas 9.7% of the children sometimes, 2.7% of them frequently and 0.9% of them very frequently display episodes of violent anger. 3.5% of the children sometimes and 1.8% of them frequently display anger when their emotional or physical needs are not met (e.g., hunger, tiredness, attention). 0.9% of the children sometimes had ever harmed themselves or others as a result of their violent anger. 3.5% of the children sometimes and

0.9% of them frequently use yelling, screaming, or name-calling when angry. 0.9% of the children sometimes had caused physical harm to others intentionally.

Item analysis- Night mares

In that selected areas 7.1% of the children sometimes experienced nightmares. 4.4% of the children sometimes typically respond upon waking from a nightmare. 5.3% of the children sometimes recall and describe their nightmares upon waking.

Item analysis- Encopresis

In that selected areas none of the children of sex workers had Encopresis.

Item analysis- Tics

In that selected areas 4.4% of the children of sex workers sometimes experienced tics or repetitive movements. 2.7% of the children sometimes and 0.9% of them frequently exhibit sudden, repetitive movements, such as blinking or head jerking.

Item analysis- Stammering

In that selected areas 4.4% of the children of sex workers sometimes and 0.9% of them frequently had difficulty speaking. 2.7% of them sometimes had stammering increased or decreased in frequency or intensity over time. 0.9% of them sometimes had stammering appear to be increased by events or other factors. 1.8% of them sometimes had speech disruptions occur frequently or regularly. 1.8% of them sometimes had avoidance behaviours related to speaking, such as avoiding certain words or situations.

Section III

Analysis of data related to association between selected demographic variables of children of sex workers and behavioural problems.

Demographic variable		Behavioural problems		p-value
		Behavioural problem	No behavioural problem	
Age	3-6 years	15	34	0.001
	6-9 years	24	17	
	9-12 years	17	6	
Gender	Male	29	29	1.000
	Female	27	28	
Education	Currently enrolled in school	19	33	0.014
	Not enrolled in school	37	24	
Care taker	Mother	38	35	0.397
	Foster Parents	14	20	
	Other relative	4	2	
Exposure to violence	Yes	8	4	0.238
	No	48	53	

Fisher's exact test for the association between selected demographic variables of children of sex workers and behavioural problems.

Since p-values corresponding to age and education were small (less than 0.05), the demographic variables age and education were found to have significant association with the behavioral problem among children of sex workers.

Conclusion

The study found that many children of sex workers showed signs of behavioral problems. Out of 113 children, 13.3% had violent anger, 8.8% had bedwetting (enuresis), 8% bite their nails, 7.1% had nightmares, 5.3% sucked their thumbs, 5.3% stammered, and 4.4% had tics. None of the children had problems with passing stool (encopresis). These results show the need for early support and care to help these children cope and develop in a healthy way.

Discussion

This study was done to find out how common behavioural problems are among children of sex workers in selected areas of the city. The aim was also to create an information booklet on how to prevent and manage these issues. A total of 113 children were studied using a self-structured rating scale. The research followed a quantitative, non-experimental descriptive design, and data was collected using convenient sampling.

The tool used for assessment was validated by experts and found to be reliable. Ethical clearance was taken, and consent was obtained from participants and their mothers. Data collection was done over 30 days.

The results showed that: 13.3% of children had violent anger, 8.8% had enuresis (bedwetting), 8% bit their nails, 7.1% had nightmares, 5.3% sucked their thumbs, 5.3% stammered, 4.4% had tics and None had encopresis.

These findings highlight the need for early support and awareness to manage behavioral problems in this vulnerable group.

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Conflict of interest: There are no conflicts of interest.

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